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R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
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PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
SEN: Sensitive, limited under conditions of the Grant Agreement

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Abstract:	The Data Management Plan (DMP) details the types of data the project will generate, how this data will be managed, stored, and shared, and the extent to which it will be made available for verification and reuse or for exploitation. It also clarifies the data management responsibilities of project participants. As a dynamic document, the DMP will be updated and refined throughout the INERRANT research project’s life cycle.
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Executive Summary

This document is the deliverable “D8.3 Data Management Plan (DMP)” of the European project “INERRANT – Integrating novel materials with scalable processes for safer and recyclable Li-ion batteries” (Grant Agreement (GA) number 101147457).

This initial version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) establishes a general framework for managing data within the INERRANT project. It provides an overview of the datasets to be collected and details the methodology for generating, accessing, reusing, curating, storing, preserving, and utilizing data. Specifically, the document outlines the general data management policy, procedures for data and metadata collection and publication, types of data to be generated, options for data security and storage, accessibility considerations (distinguishing between publicly accessible data and data restricted to consortium members and the European Commission (EC)), resource allocation, and ethical aspects of data management.

The INERRANT Data Management Plan (DMP) will ensure that the consortium’s approach to research data management adheres to the FAIR principles—making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. It will also uphold the principle of making INERRANT data “as open as possible and as closed as necessary,” supporting openness to the wider research community, potential future collaborators, and other stakeholders. As a dynamic document, the DMP will be updated and refined throughout the project’s duration.

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Terms and abbreviations

2FA	2-Factor Authentication
AIF	Audio Interchange File
ASCII	American Standard Code for Information Interchange
BMP	Bitmap
CC-BY-SA	Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike
CERN	European Organization for Nuclear Research
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
D&E&C	Dissemination-Exploitation-Communication
DLP	Data Loss Prevention
DMC	Data Management Committee
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOC/DOCX	Microsoft Word
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FORTH/ICEHT	Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas/Institute of Chemical Engineering Sciences (Project coordinator)
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HEU	Horizon Europe
HTML	Hypertext Mark-up Language
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
JPEG	Joint Photographic Experts Group
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
MARCXML	MARC 21 format in XML
MOV	QuickTime Multimedia File
MP3	MPEG-1 Audio Layer 3
MPEG	Moving Picture Experts Group
ODS	OpenDocument Spreadsheet
ODT	OpenDocument Text
PDF	Portable Document Format
PI	Persistent Identifier
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
PSD	Photoshop
RTF	Rich Text Format
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
SSL/TLS	Secure Sockets Layer and Transport Layer Security
TIFF	Tag Image File Format
TXT	Text File
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WAV	Waveform Audio Format
WMV	Windows Media Video

WP	Work Package
XLS/XLSX	Microsoft Excel
XML	Extensible Markup Language

1. Introduction

A Data Management Plan (DMP) is an essential document that specifies how data will be managed throughout and beyond a Horizon Europe (HEU) project to ensure it remains well-organized, accessible, and preserved. The DMP establishes the FAIR data principles to enhance the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of research data. These principles lay the groundwork for enabling efficient discovery and use of data and metadata by both humans and machines.

This document follows the Horizon 2020 (H2020) template provided by the European Commission for Data Management Plans [1] and includes the following sections:

- Section 2 provides a brief overview of the data to be collected or generated for INERRANT, detailing its origin, whether it is new, reused, or derived from existing data.
- Section 3 outlines the three repositories to be utilized in the INERRANT project.
- Section 4 describes the data management procedures that will be implemented.
- Section 5 presents the FAIR guidelines to facilitate data sharing, comprehension, and usability for current and future researchers as well as machines.
- Section 6 details the resources and methods for data storage during and after the project.
- Section 7 addresses protections against unauthorized data access.
- Section 8 discusses ethical considerations related to data collection and sharing, especially concerning human subjects.
- Section 9 defines roles and responsibilities for data management, storage, and sharing within INERRANT.
- Section 10 summarizes the overall data management strategy and objectives for the INERRANT project.

The INERRANT DMP will be updated at each periodic review or assessment of the project, with a final version prepared for the concluding review. Additionally, updates are expected whenever significant changes occur, such as the introduction of new datasets, adjustments to consortium policies, or the influence of external factors.

2. Data summary

2.1 Project structure and data flows

The technical work of INNERANT, set over a strategic 3-year horizon (36 M), is meticulously structured into eight pivotal Work Packages (WPs). These WPs encompass five that are deeply technical, one that underscores the importance of recyclability and sustainability, and two that are dedicated to D&E&C activities (WP7) and Project Management (WP8). Each WP, its individual tasks, and their intricate interrelations are not just by design but are strategically shaped to not only meet but exceed the project's KPIs, through collaborative activities among the beneficiaries. The structure of the work plan is schematically illustrated in the PERT diagram shown in Fig. 3.1.

Figure 1. INERRANT structure (PERT) illustrating the interplay and synergistic interactions among the diverse Work Packages

WP7 and WP8 operate concurrently serving as the backbone of the project, ensuring its seamless and efficient management, careful scientific coordination, and proactive stakeholder engagement, facilitating cooperation between beneficiaries to ensure successful progress of the project. WP8, in particular, provides efficient project management, ensuring that every milestone is met with precision and excellence. It fosters a culture of collaboration, ensuring that every partner is aligned with the project's vision and adheres to Open Science principles. WP7, on the other hand, is the project's outreach arm, devising comprehensive dissemination activities. It ensures that the INERRANT's innovations are not just confined to labs and the scientific community but reach diverse stakeholders, from industry experts to the general public. WP5 stands as a testament to the INERRANT's commitment to sustainability. It consolidates all necessary tools for a robust LCA, LCC, S-LCA as also a novel recyclability processes, ensuring that these processes are in perfect alignment with the project's breakthrough technologies. It will delineate the roadmap to realize the ambitious vision to achieve project objectives for safe and sustainable by design material development for Gen 3 LIBs. WP1, WP2, and WP3 represent the technically innovative parts of the proposed work in regard to materials and eco-friendly processes development, needed to achieve safer and better performing anode, cathode, electrolyte and separator for Gen 3 LIBs. The advances of novel LIB components will be integrated in WP4. A two-step upscaling approach is followed; first, with small-scale pouch cells to evaluate the cell manufacturing process and scalability of materials, and second, by technology demonstration at large-scale cells compatible with electromobility applications. WP6 deals with extensive LIB cell safety testing and analysis applying international testing standards (e.g. EUCAR, IEC, UN). It employs validated protocols to not just expedite market adoption but to ensure that the products stand up to the highest safety and performance standards, with a safety benchmark set ambitiously at (at least) the Hazard Level of 3.

2.2 Origin of the data

In order to have an initial, clear and overarching view of what kinds of data will be generated or collected from the research outputs of the project, all partners were asked to complete the questionnaire in “**Appendix A. Questionnaire on expected Research Outputs for Data Management Plan (DMP)**” The responses given are summarized in the tables and in the paragraphs below.

Table 1. Collected / generated data summary

Collected / generated data	Data support the project objectives by:
Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas (FORTH)	
Raw measurement data from optical spectroscopies	Providing information for graphene quality.
Raw measurement data from electron microscopies	Providing information for electrode morphology.
Raw measurement data from electrochemical techniques	Providing information for device performance.
Raw measurement data from surface-related photoemission spectroscopies	Providing information for surface chemistry details.
Tables, figures, etc. (generated)	Contributing to the preparation of reports, presentations, articles, etc.
PLEIONE Energy SA (PLE)	
Test data	Development evaluation
Physical objects (battery cells)	Demonstration and testing
Photos and other audio/visual material	Data and results presentation, dissemination, communication, exploitation activities
University of Jan Evangelista Purkyně (UJEP)	
Various designs of polymer solution systems to be tested on laboratory scale	Composition and ratios of materials
SEM of nanofibers	Electron microscopy images
Mechanical properties of nanofibers	Graphs in Origin
FTIR of nanofibers	Graphs
Other physic-chemical properties	Graphs, tables in Origin, Excel etc.

Report including recycling process	Complete report with data collected during development
Reports including description of complete process of development	Complete report with data collected during development
NanoSpace Technology s.r.o. (NST)	
Various designs of polymer solution systems to be tested on laboratory and industrial scale	Composition and ratios of materials
SEM of nanofibers	Electron microscopy images
Material data sheets	Description of materials produced
Reports including description of complete process of development	Complete report with data collected during development
SOP – standard operation process	Document describing complete process of production of nanofiber based membranes
KEYSIGHT (KEYS)	
Raw impedance measurement data of prototype and commercial LIB cells.	LIB pouch cell metrological evaluation and traceable calibrations towards industrialization.
Calibrated impedance spectroscopy data (Generated).	LIB pouch cell metrological evaluation and traceable calibrations towards industrialization.
Micro-Ampere self-discharge data of prototype battery cells from INERRANT (Generated).	Definition of battery cell hazard level for e-mobility applications-
Figures, tables, and diagrams. (Generated)	Supporting implementation of novel performance testing processes for innovation acceleration. Dissemination and publication activities.

Table 2. Re-used data summary

Data that will be re-used in order to:	Origin of the re-used data	Restrictions of the re-used data
Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas (FORTH)		
Optimize new data collected within the project	Data obtained by of FORTH in the course of previous studies	Confidential

Compare them with new data obtained within the project	Literature data on similar investigations	Tables or graphs comparing re-used and new data will be published in reports and articles
PLEIONE Energy SA (PLE)		
Test data	Previous projects deliverables and reports	Restricted under license
University of Jan Evangelista Purkyně (UJEP)		
Data, experiences and information from previous projects	Our previously obtained unpublished and restricted data	Confidential
NanoSpace Technology s.r.o. (NST)		
Data, experiences and information from previous projects which will be used to develop new materials	Property of nanoSPACE Technology	Confidential
KEYSIGHT (KEYS)		
Battery impedance data to calibrate the test system and for verification purpose.	Keysight generated data with stakeholder.	Confidential

It's worthwhile to mention that there are no applicable national, funder, sector-specific or institutional procedures for data management that regulate any partner's handling of research data.

The Data Origin section will be expanded over the project's life cycle, with more comprehensive information provided in subsequent DMP versions on:

1. Data Collection Methods: Detailed descriptions of the techniques and processes used to gather or generate data (e.g., experiments, observations, sensors, simulations).
2. Existing Datasets: Identification of dataset sources (e.g., publicly available, obtained from repositories, or acquired through previous research) and the processing or modifications applied to incorporate them into the project.
3. Data Provenance: Steps to track and document any changes, ensuring a clear and transparent lineage of the dataset.

2.3 Data types and formats

The data types and formats outlined in this section were initially gathered from partners' responses to the questionnaire in Appendix A and will be updated as the project progresses.

Data types

The following is a preliminary, non-exhaustive list of data types identified at this initial stage in INERRANT:

- Publication
- Presentation
- Poster
- Dataset
- Report
- Software
- Text
- Image
- Audiovisual
- Workflow
- Model representation
- Collection
- Physical object

Data formats

Table 3 provides the recommended data formats for use in INERRANT.

Table 3. The recommended data formats in INERRANT

Type of data	Recommended formats
<p>Quantitative tabular data with minimal metadata.</p> <p>A matrix of data with or without column headings or variable names, but no other metadata or labeling.</p>	<p>Comma-separated values (CSV) file (.csv).</p> <p>Widely-used formats: MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx), OpenDocument Spreadsheet (.ods).</p>
<p>Quantitative tabular data with extensive metadata.</p>	<p>Some structured text or mark-up file containing metadata information, e.g. XML file.</p>

A dataset with variable labels, code labels, and defined missing values, in addition to the matrix of data.	
Qualitative data. Textual. Documentation and scripts.	Plain text data, ASCII (.txt). Rich Text Format (.rtf). Widely-used proprietary formats: MS Word (.doc/.docx), MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx). OpenDocument Text (.odt). Hypertext Mark-up Language (.html). PDF/A or PDF (.pdf).
Digital image data.	TIFF (uncompressed) (.tif, .tiff). PNG (.png). JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg). BMP (.bmp). Photoshop files (.psd).
Digital audio data.	MPEG-1 Audio Layer 3 (.mp3). Waveform Audio Format (.wav). Audio Interchange File Format (.aif).
Digital video data.	MPEG-4 (.mp4). MOV (.mov) Windows Media Video (WMV) (.wmv).

2.4 Sensitive data

While much of the data generated or collected in INERRANT will be publicly accessible, some data will be classified as confidential due to its commercial value or because it contains personal information that cannot be fully anonymized.

Confidential data will be accessible either to all partners or restricted to a designated subset of partners, referred to as "data owners." The first category of confidential data is termed "**Restricted data**", accessible to all partners, and the second category is "**Closed data**", limited to specific data owners only.

Restricted data produced in INERRANT will be stored in the INERRANT Project Management Platform (<https://inerrant.eurice.eu>), provided by EURICE and granting access to all partners, while Closed data will be housed in private spaces managed by the relevant data owners. FORTH/ICEHT has created and maintains these private spaces within its Information and Communication Technology (ICT) infrastructure (<https://cloud.iceht.forth.gr/drive>), which includes robust security measures and is recommended for storing Closed data.

The access levels for data within the INERRANT project will be determined by data characteristics, ethical and legal considerations, and the data-sharing policies of the beneficiaries. At this initial stage, four access levels are defined:

- **Open:** Data is made publicly available with minimal restrictions.
- **Embargoed:** Data access is temporarily restricted, with plans for future public release after a set period.
- **Restricted:** Data access is provided to all partners under specific conditions.
- **Closed:** Highly sensitive data is accessible only to a select group of individuals involved in its production or use.

3. INERRANT repositories

In the INERRANT project, we will utilize the Zenodo repository for sharing publicly accessible open data, along with two private repositories: (a) the INERRANT Project Management Platform, for content accessible to all project beneficiaries, and (b) the Private Spaces managed by FORTH/ICEHT for sharing data with specific stakeholders.

3.1 Zenodo

INERRANT's approach ensures that all data relevant to stakeholders is accessible through open access publications or their electronic supplements.

Zenodo [2], a free open-access repository, enables researchers to deposit datasets, research software, reports, and other research materials. Created by the OpenAIRE EU project and CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research) [3] and launched in 2013, Zenodo facilitates sharing and preserving scientific data, including publications, datasets, and software. It supports open science principles, providing tools for researchers to share findings with the public, promoting open collaboration, and encouraging transparency and reproducibility in research.

A key feature of Zenodo is its assignment of a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to each submission, allowing for easy citation and ensuring long-term access and preservation of the data. In alignment with the H2020 Open Access Mandate [4], INERRANT will use Zenodo to upload scientific publications, public deliverables, and publicly accessible datasets.

The INERRANT community collection on Zenodo is available at the following URL (https://zenodo.org/communities/INERRANT_heurope).

If any additional data relevant to stakeholders cannot be included in the publications or their supplements, it will be made available through a repository.

For data that cannot be publicly shared due to confidentiality requirements (see 2.4 Sensitive Data) but remains relevant to stakeholders, it is recommended to store it in an internal repository—either the INERRANT Project Management Platform for Restricted data or the FORTH/ICEHT private spaces for Closed data. **Zenodo can also be used to publish metadata for these datasets.**

3.2 INERRANT Project Management Platform

To facilitate communication among all INERRANT partners, EURICE developed an internal Project Management Platform accessible exclusively to consortium members through a password-protected system. This platform is built on the Redmine [5] system and provides a range of useful functions for daily operations. Figure 2 shows its basic layout.

Figure 2. INERRANT Project Management Platform basic layout

Every INERRANT member, who has been granted access to Project Management Platform, is able to edit its content and a history record of revisions made to each post is maintained.

3.3 FORTH/ICEHT private spaces

FORTH/ICEHT has established and maintains private storage spaces in its own ICT infrastructure (<https://cloud.iceht.forth.gr/drive>), equipped with robust security measures, and it is recommended to be used for Closed data storage by the data owners (see 2.4 Sensitive data).

Communication with these private spaces is fully SSL/TLS (Secure Sockets Layer and Transport Layer Security) encrypted and login to them is highly protected by a 2-Factor Authentication (2FA) security process (Figure 3).

Figure 3. FORTH/ICEHT private spaces login process

Upon successfully logging into a private space, a user is able to effortlessly create a folder and establish his/her own unique access requirements for it. For example, the folder shown in Figure 4 was set up with varying access permissions for three individuals interested in viewing and modifying the folder's contents.

FORTH/ICEHT private spaces are accessible via Web and also by using the appropriate desktop (Windows, MacOS, Linux) and mobile (Android, Apple iOS) applications.

Figure 4. An example of assigning different folder access permissions in FORTH/ICEHT private spaces

4. INERRANT procedure for data management

Figure 5 illustrates the main procedure used in the INERRANT project for data management.

When a new research data is collected or generated during the project, the corresponding scientist (**Data provider**) submits it to the **Data Management Committee (DMC)** for approval. The DMC reviews data, based on its metadata information, detailed descriptions provided by the provider, or any other relative information from third-party sources such as stakeholders, public bodies, society etc., and approves it for further processing or not.

If the research data is approved by the DMC, then it is characterized as a **Public** or a **Confidential (Restricted or Closed)** data.

In the case of public open access data, the DMC checks its FAIRness, i.e., evaluates how well the data complies with FAIR principles for making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. Following this evaluation, the data is passed on to the **Dissemination team**, who are responsible for appropriately distributing it across various public platforms such as Zenodo, the public website, X, LinkedIn, YouTube, and others.

In the case of confidential data, the DMC carefully considers the legal, ethical, and security measures, along with licensing and intellectual property concerns, to ensure that sensitive information is adequately protected throughout the project life cycle. Subsequently, this sensitive data is either stored in the INERRANT Project Management Platform, accessible to all beneficiaries, or in a **Private space**, restricted to the data owners and specific authorized users. For the latter scenario, the use of FORTH/ICEHT private spaces is advised.

Managing confidential data is an ongoing process that requires vigilance, adherence to best practices, and an understanding of the evolving landscape of data privacy and security. Ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of sensitive data protects beneficiaries' properties, maintains trust, and complies with legal obligations.

Figure 5. INERRANT procedure for data management

4.1 A comprehensive list of INERRANT research outputs

The "**Research Outputs**" section of the INERRANT Project Management Platform displays a comprehensive list of data that has been generated or collected up to this point in the INERRANT project.

When a new research data is collected or generated during the project, the responsible scientist (**Data provider**) adds a new entry to the Research Outputs list (Figure 6), providing some initial necessary information on it such as:

- **Title:** The title of the research output.
- **Description:** A short description of the research output.
- **Data Collection Method:** Detailed description of the techniques and processes used to gather or generate data (e.g., experiments, observations, sensors, simulations). The use or not of pre-existing datasets have to be defined here.
- **WP:** In which Work Package does this research output be collected or generated? Single selection among {WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7, WP8} choices.
- **Type:** The type of the research output. Single selection among {Publication, Presentation, Poster, Dataset, Report, Software, Text, Image, Audiovisual, Workflow, Model representation, Collection, Physical object} choices. The user can add values manually.
- **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR):** Does this research output contain personally identifiable information? Single selection among {Yes, No} choices.
- **Access level:** The access level of the research output. Single selection among {Open, Embargoed, Restricted, Closed} choices.
- **Stored at:** The repository where the research output is stored. Single selection among {Zenodo, Public website, Project Management Platform, Social media, Private space} choices.
- **URL / PI:** The Uniform Resource Locator (URL) or the Persistent Identifier (PI) of the research output.
- **License:** The license of the research output. Single selection among {CC-BY-4.0, CC-BY-NC-4.0, CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0, CC Zero} choices. The User can add values manually.
- **Notes:** Some extra notes regarding this research output.
- **Attachments:** Some useful files (e.g., metadata) may be added here.

Additionally, the system automatically appends the **name of the User** who adds the new item, along with the **Date it was created**, to this entry.

Upon the addition of new research data to the Research Outputs list, the **DMC** members are notified to follow the steps outlined in the previously described data management procedure. If the DMC approves the data, the respective field is updated to 'Yes,' and the '**Approval date**' field is accurately filled out.

New item

Title
Enter value here

Description *
Enter value here
A short description of the research output.

Data Collection Method *
Enter value here
Detailed description of the techniques and processes used to gather or generate data (e.g., experiments, observations, sensors, simulations). The use or not of pre-existing datasets have to be defined here.

WP *
—
In which Work Package does this research output be collected or generated?

Type *
—
The type of the research output

GDPR *
—
Does your research outputs contain personally identifiable information?

Access level *
—
The access level of the research output

Stored at *
—
The repository where the research output is stored

URL / PI
Enter a URL
Alternative text (optional)
The URL or the Persistent Identifier of the research output

Approved by DMC?
 Yes
Is the research output sharing approved by Data Management Committee?

Approval Date
Enter a date
The date that the DMC approved the sharing of the research output

License
—
The license of the research output

Notes
Enter value here
Some extra notes regarding this research output

Attachments
Add attachments

Save **Cancel**

Figure 6. The data entry form for a research output

5. FAIR data

5.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

The INERRANT project emphasizes the findability, discoverability, and identifiability of its research data. In line with document management guidelines, each document version is clearly identified at the beginning, and file names include at least a version number and/or timestamp.

All project-generated data, except the closed confidential data, is consolidated in the INERRANT Project Management Platform, a primary repository for consortium members, equipped with a robust internal search engine.

Open access data from the INERRANT project is uploaded to the INERRANT community collection on Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/INERRANT_heurope). Each submission is enhanced with Zenodo's standard metadata, including the Grant Number and Project Acronym, to facilitate organization and identification. Zenodo ensures version control and assigns DOIs to each uploaded item, enhancing the traceability and citation of the data. The metadata for each dataset published on Zenodo is set to include the following default information:

- Digital Object Identifiers
- Bibliographic information
- Keywords
- Abstract/description
- Associated project and community
- Associated publications and reports
- Grant information with the project name and GA number
- Access and licensing info
- Language

Also, for the public, data is disseminated through the project's website (<https://www.inerrant-batteries.eu>), employing standard Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) strategies to enhance data visibility and discoverability based on specific keywords.

5.2 Making data openly accessible

The Horizon Open Access Mandate ensures that research data produced by HEU projects remains accessible while safeguarding personal and sensitive information when privacy, commercial interests, or security concerns arise. This mandate promotes open dissemination of all public datasets, scientific publications, and deliverables from the INERRANT project. Specifically, project deliverables marked as public in the Description of Action will be shared openly via the project's website (<https://www.inerrant-batteries.eu>) and through the INERRANT community collection on Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/INERRANT_heurope). To enhance connectivity and discoverability, publications and their corresponding datasets will be linked through persistent identifiers (DOIs), ensuring version control.

For datasets classified as "confidential," sharing will be restricted to protect commercial interests.

The project's publications will primarily follow the 'gold open access' model, with some outputs also available through 'green open access.' Zenodo will be the main repository for self-archiving under green open access. For gold open access, compliance with scientific publishers' open access policies, including any embargo periods, is necessary to meet EC open access requirements, and the selected publishing platform must assign a DOI to each publication to ensure accessibility standards.

Additionally, efforts will be made to feature publications on the project's website, provided this aligns with publishers' copyright policies. This strategy not only supports the Horizon Open Access Mandate's objectives but also underscores a commitment to broadening access to scientific discoveries while respecting legal and ethical guidelines.

5.3 Making data interoperable

As data collection and generation continue, establishing exact steps to ensure data interoperability remains challenging at this stage. The evolving nature of data acquisition requires an adaptable approach, focusing on standards and formats that support ease of use and compatibility across systems and disciplines as datasets are further defined.

The anticipated types of raw data, such as ASCII or TXT, are broadly compatible with widely used software packages like ORIGIN, MATLAB, MATHEMATICA, and Excel, facilitating accessibility and analysis. Similarly, microscopic image data, typically in formats like JPEG or TIFF, will be compatible with various image processing software, ensuring flexibility in data handling as the project progresses.

Moreover, Zenodo uses a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) schema for its metadata structure, allowing conversion into multiple formats such as MARCXML (MARC 21 in XML) and BibTeX (for reference management), supporting integration with Mendeley. Zenodo's metadata structure aligns with its specific vocabularies and references external vocabularies for elements like licenses (Open Definition) and funders (FundRef, Funder Registry), using resolvable URLs for external metadata. This approach improves metadata interoperability and accessibility, ensuring wide compatibility and ease of use for research and academic applications.

5.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

The INERRANT project is dedicated to providing external parties with the ability to access, use, replicate, and share all datasets classified as public. To maximize the potential for broad reuse, the consortium is committed to implementing open licensing frameworks wherever feasible. This approach will prioritize the use of common, standardized, and globally recognized licensing models. For example, the consortium plans to adopt the 'CC-BY-SA 4.0' (Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0) license as a foundational standard for licensing research data, promoting maximum reuse.

Final decisions regarding data publication and sharing—including license selection and release timing—will require a thorough review process once the project's data sources are carefully selected and evaluated for relevance and suitability. This strategic approach ensures data dissemination decisions are informed by a comprehensive understanding of the data's nature and implications, aligning with project goals and adhering to legal and ethical standards. This careful approach highlights

the project's commitment to an open and collaborative research environment, promoting responsible and effective knowledge sharing.

6. Allocation of resources

In INERRANT project we will use the Zenodo repository for sharing public open access data, as well as two private repositories: (a) the INERRANT Project Management Platform, for making content available to all project beneficiaries, and (b) the FORTH/ICEHT private spaces for sharing data with individual stakeholders.

Zenodo [2] is a free and open access repository, hosted by CERN [3], and there is no cost for its use. With its virtually limitless storage capacity, Zenodo ensures that concerns about adequate storage space will not arise throughout the INERRANT project. Also, Zenodo supports long-term preservation of data deposits, as the repository is projected to be maintained for the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, defined as at least the next twenty years (see Zenodo's Policies [6]).

The INERRANT Project Management Platform has been set up by EURICE based on the Redmine [5] system. This platform is provided free of cost to the consortium, and the EURICE guarantees sufficient storage space as well as data accessibility for at least five years following the project's conclusion.

FORTH/ICEHT offers and maintains private storage spaces within its ICT infrastructure at no charge to the consortium. Initially, 200GB of storage space is allocated for INERRANT, with the possibility of expansion if necessary. FORTH commits to keeping the data accessible for a minimum of five years after the completion of the project.

Expenses associated with managing research data qualify for coverage under the project grant. The tasks involved in generating, collecting, and curating data fall within the scope of person-months (and thus are considered direct personnel costs), as outlined in the GA for each partner. Also, every partner has designated funds to ensure data availability through open access publications.

There is no anticipation of resource allocation beyond what is already committed to the project. However, if additional costs are foreseen, this will be included in an update of the DMP.

7. Data security

Zenodo's entire technical infrastructure is located on CERN's premises and follows CERN's data security policies and measures [7], which ensures integrity, authenticity, accountability and prevention of data breaches. Regarding availability and longevity, Zenodo provides data files versioning, replicas, preservation and succession plans [6].

INERRANT Project Management Platform is hosted at EURICE's premises which offers a comprehensive security framework, which provides multi-layered security, leveraging custom hardware with integrated security controls and protection against threats such as DDoS (Distributed Denial-of-Service) attacks.

FORTH/ICEHT provides a comprehensive suite of security measures to protect data and infrastructure within the cloud environment, in order to maintain the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data and sharing service. These include encryption of data both in transit and at rest, Data Loss Prevention

(DLP) tools to prevent unauthorized access or exposure, and regular backups for data recovery in case of incidents. Also, FORTH/ICEHT provides visibility into malicious activity by aggregating data from across the environment, supporting incident response and alert qualification, and has capabilities to identify data threats and respond quickly, using global cybersecurity intelligence and real-time data analysis.

8. Ethical aspects

The ethical dimensions of the INERRANT project will be addressed under WP8.

Key obligations of the project, regarding data collection ethics, include:

- The appointment of a Data Management Committee (DMC), which will address all ethical data collection issues.
- The establishment of standardized procedures, including security and confidentiality protocols and consent templates for any personal data collection, in accordance with GDPR principles. Research data will be fully protected (e.g., via pseudonymization or anonymization). Any indirect references to sensitive data (such as industrial or business data) will be removed and destroyed once the anonymized dataset is verified. Personal data will only be used when informed consent has been obtained. The DMC will securely store all consent forms in an internal, secure private space using the corresponding FORTH/ICEHT service. INERRANT Informed Consent Form is shown in **Appendix B. Informed consent form to participate in research activities of the Project INERRANT**.
- The provision of guidance to project partners on when and where approvals are required, how to handle personal data, and when informed consent is necessary, including specific procedures for obtaining consent during stakeholder communications.

9. Roles and Responsibilities

The **Data Management Committee (DMC)** is responsible for coordinating activities and recommending policies to improve data quality, consistency, security, and accessibility. Key functions of the DMC include resolving data definition discrepancies, prioritizing actions to enhance data consistency and accuracy, and recommending changes to processes, training, and systems to strengthen data quality. Additionally, the DMC advises on data access compliance policies and addresses ethical and privacy issues, serving as **an advisory and approval body** for data definitions and sources. The DMC collaborates closely with project management and technical partners to develop and periodically update the Data Management Plan, led by a designated **Data Officer**.

INERRANT's Data Management Committee consists of the following members:

Table 4. INERRANT's Data Management Committee

Name	Partner
Spyros Yannopoulos	FORTH

Athanasios Masouras	PLE
Anna Knaislová	UJEP
Serena Cussen	UCD
Michael Hoffman	FHG
Guinevere Giffin	JMU
Petr Marecek	IBG
Jan Buk	NST
Nawfal Al-Zubaidi R-Smith	KEYS
Yannick Molmeret	VER
Sam Hoefman	EURICE

Work Package Data Managers are responsible for implementing the data management plan within their respective work packages. Their responsibilities include tracking data management tasks and deadlines, sending reminders to partners, requesting any missing information or clarifications, providing targeted support and guidance for open access data publication, and ensuring that all data is fully deposited in the designated repositories.

The WP Data Managers for INERRANT are as follows:

Table 5. INERRANT WP Data Managers

WP	Name	Partner
WP1	Spyros Yannopoulos	FORTH
WP2	Serena Cussen	UCD
WP3	Jiri Orava	UJEP
WP4	Antonios Vavouliotis	PLE
WP5	Petr Marecek	IBG
WP6	Yannick Molmeret	VERKOR
WP7	Sam Hoefman	EURICE
WP8	Magda Spella	FORTH

Finally, the responsibilities of the **Data Provider/Scientist** include informing data managers of newly available data, documenting the data with required metadata in accordance with the DMP, utilizing provided tools (such as the Research Output form), and uploading the data to designated repositories following the DMP guidelines.

10. Conclusions

This document presents the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the INERRANT project. It outlines the approach to managing research data during and after the project, specifying the data to be collected, processed, and/or generated. It also defines the process for determining whether data will be publicly accessible or kept confidential and describes the strategies for curating and preserving data, including post-project preservation. Additionally, the document addresses how INERRANT data will adhere to the FAIR principles as recommended by the European Commission.

The INERRANT DMP is a living document, periodically updated throughout the project to incorporate new data, procedures, and insights from ongoing discussions within the project consortium and with stakeholders. All updates to the DMP will be included in the periodic reports.

References

- [1] TEMPLATE HORIZON 2020 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP), https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/gm/reporting/h2020-tpl-oa-data-mgt-plan-annotated_en.pdf
- [2] The Zenodo repository, <https://www.zenodo.org/>
- [3] Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire, <https://home.cern>
- [4] Horizon 2020 Mandate On Open Access To Publications, https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/open-access_en.htm
- [5] Redmine, a flexible, cross-platform and cross-database, project management web application, <https://www.redmine.org>. Redmine is open source and released under the terms of the GNU General Public License v2 (GPL).
- [6] Zenodo's Policies, <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>
- [7] Zenodo's Infrastructure, <https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>

Appendix A. Questionnaire on expected Research Outputs for Data Management Plan (DMP)

PART A. DATA SUMMARY

By filling the tables below, you will outline the data that your organization will collect or generate, including its purpose, how it aligns with the project's objectives and its types (i.e., images, raw measurements, tables, diagrams, reports etc.). Additionally, you will summarize data sourced from other projects, open research literature, internal reports etc., that will be re-used for INERRANT's purposes. Finally, you will indicate if there are procedures governing data management within your organization that should be taken into consideration in INERRANT's DMP.

Table A.1. Collected / generated data summary.

Data will be collected and/or generated in order to:	Data support the project objectives by:	Data type(s)

Table A.2. Re-used data summary.

Data that will be re-used in order to:	Origin of the re-used data	Restrictions of the re-used data

Table A.3. Existing data management procedures references.

Refer any applicable national, funder, sector-specific or institutional procedures for data management that regulate your organization's handling of research data (if applicable)

PART B. RESEARCH OUTPUTS CHARACTERISTICS

Please select any of the options below (you may have multiple options).

What will be the various forms of your research outputs?

- Publication
- Poster
- Dataset
- Report
- Software
- Text
- Image
- Audiovisual
- Workflow
- Model representation
- Collection
- Physical object
- Other, please specify: _____

What will be the various formats of your research outputs?

The following table contains the recommended file formats.

Do you agree on that?

- Yes
- No

Are there any other data formats that we should add? If so, please specify: _____

Type of data	Recommended formats
<p>Quantitative tabular data with minimal metadata.</p> <p>A matrix of data with or without column headings or variable names, but no other metadata or labeling.</p>	<p>Comma-separated values (CSV) file (.csv).</p> <p>Widely-used formats: MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx), OpenDocument Spreadsheet (.ods).</p>
<p>Quantitative tabular data with extensive metadata.</p> <p>A dataset with variable labels, code labels, and defined missing values, in addition to the matrix of data.</p>	<p>Some structured text or mark-up file containing metadata information, e.g. XML file.</p>
<p>Qualitative data.</p> <p>Textual.</p> <p>Documentation and scripts.</p>	<p>Plain text data, ASCII (.txt).</p> <p>Rich Text Format (.rtf).</p> <p>Widely-used proprietary formats: MS Word (.doc/.docx), MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx).</p> <p>OpenDocument Text (.odt).</p> <p>Hypertext Mark-up Language (.html).</p> <p>PDF/A or PDF (.pdf).</p>
<p>Digital image data.</p>	<p>TIFF (uncompressed) (.tif, .tiff).</p> <p>PNG (.png).</p> <p>JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg).</p> <p>BMP (.bmp).</p> <p>Photoshop files (.psd).</p>
<p>Digital audio data.</p>	<p>MPEG-1 Audio Layer 3 (.mp3).</p> <p>Waveform Audio Format (.wav).</p> <p>Audio Interchange File Format (.aif).</p>
<p>Digital video data.</p>	<p>MPEG-4 (.mp4).</p> <p>MOV (.mov)</p> <p>Windows Media Video (WMV) (.wmv).</p>

May your research outputs contain sensitive data?

- Yes
- No

May your research outputs contain personally identifiable information (ethical aspects)?

- Yes
- No

Which repository do you prefer to share and showcase your research outputs?

[An international list of data repositories is available @ <https://www.re3data.org/>]

- Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>)
- Other, please specify: _____

What metadata standards do you prefer to help others identify and discover the data?

[A Directory of Metadata Standards is available @ <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/>]

- Zenodo's default
- CERIF (Common European Research Information Format)
(https://eurocris.org/eurocris_archive/cerifsupport.org/cerif-in-brief/index.html)
- Other, please specify: _____

Which would be the access levels of your research outputs?

- Open
- Embargoed
- Restricted
- Closed
- Other, please specify: _____

Which would be the license of your research outputs?

[An online guide on selecting a license is available @ <https://ufal.github.io/public-license-selector>]

- CC-BY-4.0
- CC-BY-NC-4.0
- CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0
- CC0-1.0
- Other, please specify: _____

What's the anticipated total file size of your research outputs?

- Please specify: _____ MB

Which member of your Institution/Company is going to participate at the INERRANT's Data Management Committee?

Name: _____

Title / Role: _____

Email: _____

Appendix B. Informed consent form to participate in research activities of the Project INERRANT

Please read carefully this document before you sign.

You are invited to take part in activities of INERRANT project. This form contains information that will help you decide whether to join the research activities.

Key contact details

Controller of the data collected

Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas (FORTH), N. Plastira 100, Vassilika Vouton, GR-700 13 Heraklion, Crete, Greece.

Scientific coordinator / contact details

Spyros Yannopoulos, Research Director, Institute of Chemical Engineering Sciences, (ICE-HT), Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas (FORTH). email: sny@iceht.forth.gr

Key information about the INERRANT Project

Project Coordinator: FORTH

Funding Program: Horizon Europe

Website and contacts: <https://www.iceht.forth.gr/en>

Description of the research project

INERRANT is committed to pushing the boundaries of current Lithium-ion batteries (LIB) technologies by focusing on the development of innovative material combinations, advanced electrolyte formulations, and eco-friendly recycling methods that prioritise safety and recyclability. This holistic approach targets the entire battery lifecycle, from design and manufacturing to end-of-life recycling. The project leverages cutting-edge science and technology to build the foundation for safer energy storage solutions, paving the way for a future where mobility is both eco-friendly and secure.

The project lasts 3 years (running from May 2024 to April 2027) and is funded by the European Commission (contract no. 101147457), within the context of the Horizon Europe programme. There are 11 participants from 6 European countries and in particular:

- Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas (FORTH)
- PLEIONE Energy SA (PLE)
- University of Jan Evangelista Purkyně (UJEP)
- University College Dublin (UCD)
- Fraunhofer Institute for Silicate Research-ISC (FHG)
- Julius Maximilians Universität Würzburg (JMU)
- IBG Česko s.r.o. (IBG)
- NanoSpace Technology s.r.o. (NST)

- KEYSIGHT (KEYS)
- VERKOR (VER)
- EURICE (EURICE)

More information can be found at the project website: <https://www.inerrant-batteries.eu>

Personal data

Your identity data (full name, contact details) will be collected when you participate in INERRANT events (on a voluntary basis) for the purposes of the Dissemination and Communication activities of the project. Selected photographs/screenshots may be used for the communication of the project results in mass media and in publications to inform the public and / or the scientific community. Before taking any photographs/screenshots, you will be asked to give your consent. In case you wish to opt out from the capturing, you can turn off your camera or step away, and the data controller will not use your identifiable data.

Data processing / confidentiality

Where applicable, only the personal data that is absolutely necessary for conducting the relevant research will be collected and processed through the "pseudonymization" process. Your participation will remain confidential. Your personal data will receive a code number and the digital list linking your name to that number will be stored in a secure, locked digital file. When the data is used, your name will not be displayed under any circumstances. The participants' data are protected and kept safe throughout the project. After the completion of the project, the list linking your name to the code number of your data will be deleted. The data processing and analysis will be carried out by the data management committee of the project.

Applicable regulations

The protection of natural persons in relation to the processing of personal data is a fundamental right. The law provides specific rights for natural persons (data subjects) and sets specific obligations for those who keep and process such data (controllers). All applicable EU and national legal frameworks and guidelines on the protection of personal data, as derived from the application of the "General Data Protection Regulation (EU 679/2016)", are being considered in this study.

Rights of participants

In accordance with principles of research ethics and EU data protection regulations, you have rights regarding how your personal data is processed.

You have the right to be informed about your personal data collected in and to have access to them, and the right for these data to be in a portable and easily accessible form. You also have the right to request that your personal data be corrected, updated or deleted, the right to have the processing restricted, and the right to object, with the reservation of any exceptions provided for in existing European and national legislation. We acknowledge also to you, that in accordance with the aforementioned Regulation, you have the right to file a complaint to the corresponding national Data Protection Authority (complaints@dpa.gr).

We aim to fulfil all requests. In accordance with data protection legislation, some requests may be rejected.

Who to contact if you have questions

In order to exercise your rights, you may contact the Scientific Coordinator of the project (Spyros Yannopoulos). For any further information regarding FORTH's personal data protection policy, you may visit the website (www.forth.gr) or contact the Data Protection Officer of FORTH at: dpo@admin.forth.gr.

Certificate of Consent

I, the undersigned (name) hereby declare that I agree to participate in this event, in the context of the “INERRANT” Project – “INNOVATIVE PILOT LINES FOR SUSTAINABLE GRAPHENE-BASED FLEXIBLE AND STRUCTURAL ENERGY HARVESTING AND STORAGE DEVICES”.

The purpose of the activities and my rights have been explained to me in writing (in the information sheet).

I am participating voluntarily and understand that I can withdraw from the research activities³ without repercussions, at any time, and have my data deleted.

I am satisfied that the assurances of responsible and strict data governance, given by the “INERRANT” project, will be upheld.

I understand that my personal data are kept and treated as confidential as far as this research project is concerned.

I know and understand that my personal data will be kept in a secure environment and that the data controller, as well as any data processors, will take all the necessary and appropriate measures to protect the security, and in particular the confidentiality and integrity, of personal data, according to data protection legislation and the relevant guidelines.

I explicitly declare that I agree with the publication of the results of this activity in anonymous form and with the publication of selected photographs/screenshots for the promotion of the project in mass media, and / or reports/publications aimed at informing the public and / or the scientific community.

³ You may withdraw your consent to this activity, in writing to the Scientific Coordinator of the project, (Spyros Yannopoulos), email: sny@iceht.forth.gr, Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas (FORTH), Institute of Chemical Engineering Sciences, Stadiou str. Platani, Patras, Greece.

Print name (participant)

.....

Signature (participant)

.....

Date

.....

